

Lab protocols to study Solute Carrier Transporters

Construction of a Bacmid (BacMam) vector containing the SLC gene

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to transpose the gene of interest that was previously cloned into pHTBV1.1 vector into a bacmid which is eventually used to transfect Sf9 insect cells for viral particle generation. The pHTBV1.1 vector is transformed into DH10Bac™ competent *E. coli* cells. DH10Bac™ cells contain a parent bacmid with a *lacZ*-mini-*att*Tn7 fusion. Transposition occurs between the elements of the pHTBV1.1 vector and the parent bacmid in the presence of the transposition proteins provided by a helper plasmid. When the transposition is successful, the expression cassette disrupts the *lacZ* gene which helps visualize the new expression bacmid-containing cells as white bacterial colonies.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ MAX Efficiency™ DH10Bac Competent Cells (Thermo Fisher catalog number: 10361012)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Kanamycin (Sigma, catalog number: 25389-94-0)▪ Gentamycin▪ Tetracycline▪ IPTG▪ Bluo-Gal (Thermo Fisher, catalog number: 15519028)▪ S.O.C. Medium (Thermo Fisher, catalog number: 15544034)▪ Tris-HCl▪ EDTA▪ Isopropanol▪ Ethanol▪ RNase A
Equipment:	

Reagents setup

Procedure

Transposition:

1. Prepare DH10Bac selective LB-agar plates containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin, 7µg/mL gentamycin, and 10 µg/mL tetracycline for the maintenance of the bacmid, the pFB-LIC-Bse plasmid, and the helper plasmid, respectively, as well as 40 µg/mL IPTG and 100 µg/mL bluo-gal. Allow to dry at room temperature.
2. On ice, add 3 µL* of "miniprep" recombinant DNA to the 30 µL of DH10Bac or 50 µL of DH10EMBacY cells (make sure the cells are at the bottom of the container). Mix well by tapping the side of the plate. Leave the cells to rest on ice for 30 min.
*The DNA should be in the range of 100-200 ng/µL. For plasmid DNA with a lower concentration, use 5 µL. For plasmid DNA with a lower concentration, dilute 50x before plating the culture (step 6).
3. Prepare 900 µL of pre-warmed SOC medium (or 2 x LB medium) containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin, 10 µg/mL tetracycline and 1 µg/mL gentamycin.

4. Provide heat shock to the cells for 45 seconds in a 42°C water bath and return briefly to ice.
 5. Transfer the bacterial suspension into the pre-warmed medium and place in a shaker-incubator at 37°C at 700 rpm for 4-5 hours.
 6. Spread 50 µL of DH10Bac onto the selective LB-agar plates.
 7. Incubate the plates at 37°C for 48 hours covered with foil (lacZ gene dose is low because bacmid is a single copy BAC).
 8. White colonies contain recombinant DNA and the blue ones do not. To ensure only a true white colony is picked, pick a single colony and streak to dilution. Incubate at 37°C overnight.
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Bacmid Isolation

The following solutions can be prepared in-house. Alternatively, the Montage Plasmid Miniprep^{HTS} 96 Kit (Merck Millipore, catalog number: LSKP09604) can be used for high-throughput bacmid DNA production.

Solution I

- 15 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0)
- 10 mM EDTA
- 100 µg/mL RNase A

Solution II

- 0.2 N NaOH
- 1% SDS

Solution III

- 3 M potassium acetate (pH 5.5)

Solutions I and II should be filter sterilized. Store Solution I at 4°C. 3 M potassium acetate should be autoclaved and stored at 4°C.

Protocol:

1. Pick a single, re-streaked white colony and inoculate 2 mL LB medium, supplemented with 50 µg/mL Kanamycin, 7 µg/mL Gentamicin and 10 µg/mL Tetracycline. Grow up to 24 hours at 37°C shaking at 250 to 300 rpm.
2. Spin 1.5 mL at 14 000 x g for 1 minute.
3. Resuspend pellet in 0.3 mL Solution I and add 0.3 mL Solution II, gently mix and incubate for 5 minutes at RT.
4. Slowly add 0.3 mL of Solution III, mixing gently during addition (precipitation of protein and genomic *E. coli* DNA) and incubate on ice for 5 to 10 minutes.
5. Centrifuge at 14000 x g for 10 minutes and prepare a fresh tube containing 0.8 mL of absolute isopropanol.

6. Transfer supernatant to the tube containing the isopropanol and gently mix by inverting the tube several times, incubate on ice for 5 to 10 minutes (this mixture can be stored at -20°C overnight).
7. Centrifuge at 14000 x g for 15 minutes at RT.
8. Wash pellet with 0.5 mL 70% ethanol and centrifuge at 14000 x g for 5 minutes at room temperature.
9. Remove the supernatant thoroughly and air dry the pellet for 5 to 10 minutes at room temperature.
10. Dissolve the pellet in 40 µL tris-EDTA buffer by gently tapping the tube. The DNA should be ready for use within 10 minutes. Ensure the pellet is not over dried.
11. Store the DNA at -20°C. Aliquot the volume to avoid repeated freeze and thaw cycles as repeated free and thaw cycles can lead to a drastic reduction in transfection efficiency.
12. Perform a PCR analysis to verify successful transposition into the bacmid.

Additional notes

The following vector primers can be used to perform a screening PCR. They will add approximately 700 bp to the fragment size.

*pFBM-fwd caaaatgctcgtaacaactccgc
pFBM-rev tagttaagaataccagtcacatctttcac

Data availability

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.